

Developing and Implementing hands-on training on Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers

D6.1 – Project website and social media strategy (Dissemination & Outreach)

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Project website	www.diosi.eu
Project coordinator	Margaux Kersschot (UAntwerp)
Keywords	Doctoral training, transferable skills, entrepreneurship, innovation, Open Science, graduate tracking

Document info

Work Package **WP6 – Communication & Outreach**

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0.2	26/03/2021	Marina Sánchez Moreno	The Brand. Diosi logo
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List of acronyms and abbreviations

DIOSI	Developing and Implementing hands-on training on Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers
EC	European Commission
ECR	Early Career Researchers
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OI&E	Open Innovation & Entrepreneurship
OS	Open Science

Executive summary

This deliverable (6.1) of the DIOSI project explains the work done until month 6 (M6, June 2021) to promote the communication of research activities, news and results of the project, and to multiple audiences (scientific community but also media and general public).

We describe the process of building a brand image for the project in order to give consistency and promote the recognition among partners and other stakeholders. Once the brand was approved by the consortium members, we developed a website as the main outreach channel and set up social media accounts on Twitter and Youtube. Moreover, we define the strategy and some key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess the progress of an effective communication.

- ✓ Website: <https://www.diosi.eu>
- ✓ E-mail: diosi.eu@gmail.com
- ✓ Twitter: [@diosiproject](https://twitter.com/diosiproject). <https://twitter.com/diosiproject>
- ✓ Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChp_q_Glj3Dql1vfqgi5JZA

1. The Brand. DIOSI Logo design

ABOUT DIOSI

“The DIOSI project proposes a full cycle concept on doctoral education, from the development of a new joint doctoral educational programme, through the provision of training on Open Science and Open Innovation & Entrepreneurship for doctoral candidates and early career researchers (DCs and ECRs), to the measurement of impact of such training, by creating an impact and graduate tracking framework.”

*CORDIS. EU research results
European Commission*

DIOSI partners are also YUFE (Young Universities for the Future of Europe European University Alliance) partners .

CYCLE DESIGN

CYCLE

Full cycle concept on doctoral education.

DIOSI is placed in the center of the circle, filling a space that represents the gap in education this project aims to fill.

The open circle and the small circles placed in descending order gives the idea of a field in expansion (Open Science).

COLOR & TYPOGRAPHY

Typogrphy (Montserrat) and colors are in harmony with YUFE logo, so that they “get along” with each other when they appear one next to the other.

CONCLUSIONS

Besides the creation of the logo and in order to reinforce the recognition of the communication of the project, we designed 2 templates with 24 different designs for PowerPoint or similar software and 1 deliverable template (metadata of the document, typography, colors, etc.) for Word, Libre or Open Office for deliverables.

2. Internal Communication

Members of the consortium agreed to store key internal documents in the Microsoft Teams workspace of the project leader (University of Antwerp) and periodical meetings and internal reports are discussed and updated through this Microsoft Teams workspace and videoconferencing system. As an alternative partners use also Zoom videoconferencing tools and everything is flowing smoothly and with no problems until now.

3. Communication & Outreach

DIOSI project planned the Communication & Outreach as a separated work package, WP6, one of the option. The aim of this work package is to ensure the communication of the project's results and the communication to a broader audience by organizing diffusion events and using appropriate communication tools with four main tasks and one deliverable on month 6 for the launch of the website.

Task 6.1 consists in the creation of a project website and social media propagation to provide general and specific information about the project, updates of activities and publish the reports from the other work-packages. Throughout the project, UC3M will post updates on the website and social media.

This deliverable is a short description of the website information architecture and design of this web site as well as a brief description of the communication policy and strategy for the website and the social media accounts linked and used as channels to get more impact and spread results and events of the project to multiple audiences.

3.1 The website

The project website is under the domain diosi.eu and is working under a secure http protocol (<https://www.diosi.eu> or <https://diosi.eu>) and hosted by a European company with servers and backup in Europe. The web server is running on WordPress.

Information architecture of the web site is structured in six different areas under a sticky main menu. These areas are:

1. About. Information about the project, partners, advisory board and contacts.
2. News, mainly about training on Open Innovation and Open Science for Early Career Researchers, not only from the project but also from other European projects like DocEnhance or from European universities, especially those that belong to the YUFE Alliance.
3. Events have also a special space in the website because several work packages will organize courses and meetings.
4. Resources space is devoted to scientific and training resources about Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers.
5. Project outputs are the space where we publish and communicate our public reports.
6. The Members Area is a private space for Diosi partners (files storage and other non for public information).

The first area (About) is only accessible by dropping down the menu because it's a very static information so this first area is filled with the title and a representative image of the project and the timeline of the Diosi Twitter account plus the feed from some hashtags related to the project. All these workspaces are surrounded by a short menu for social media accounts and the acknowledgement of EU funding at the bottom of the Home Page.

Figure 1. Diosi project website Home Page

News

CAREER-TRACKING TO PHD GRADUATES: 2,200 RESPONSES!

Colleagues from the DocEnhance Project collected 2,000 responses from their career-tracking survey. They asked PhD graduates from eight universities across Europe about their careers since graduation. The aim was to explore: the types of jobs taken by PhD students after graduation and their relation to the training received; how the skills they developed during their...

[Read more >](#)

GOOGLE TRENDS ON OPEN SCIENCE

CALL FOR EXPERTS

Dear all, What does implementing the FAIR data principles in universities mean in reality? How can it be rolled out on the ground among researchers and students? What are the expectations of doing this in a diverse multi-disciplinary environment? To start to solve these challenges, we are holding a Book Sprint in June to develop...

[Read more >](#)

Resources

Diosi Project Trailer

Develop and disseminate a model for doctoral training, integrating both transferable and research skills

Basics of Open and Responsible Science: Open Access Publishing and Research Data

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Ut elit tellus, luctus nec ullamcorper mattis, pulvinar dapibus leo.

Articles, reports & more

The Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (2016)

This report presents the EntreComp Framework. By producing a common definition of what entrepreneurship as a competence is, the framework aims to establish a bridge between the worlds of education and work and to be taken as a reference de facto by any initiative which aims to foster entrepreneurial learning. The framework is a flexible source of inspiration, to be used or adapted to support different contexts. For instance, EntreComp could inspire the reform of curricula in the formal education and training sector, the design of practical entrepreneurial experiences in non-formal learning contexts, or the development of tools for citizens to self-assess their entrepreneurial proficiency.

The EntreComp Framework is made up of 3 competence areas: 'Ideas and opportunities', 'Resources' and 'Into action'. Each area includes 5 competences, which, together, are the building blocks of entrepreneurship as a competence. The framework develops the 15 competences along an 8-level progression model. Also, it provides a comprehensive list of 442 learning outcomes, which offers inspiration and insight for those designing interventions from different educational contexts and domains of application.

More info: [JRC Science for Policy Report – EntreComp: The Entrepreneurship Competence Framework \(2016\)](#)

Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science (2021)

Digital skills for FAIR and open science are a cornerstone of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)'s operations and future. An EOSC network of skilled professionals is essential to bring a culture change for sharing research outcomes, and to empower individuals and institutions to develop and maintain EOSC competences, skills and capabilities.

Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science The EOSC Skills and Training Working Group (WG) was formed in 2020 to identify a framework for building competence and capabilities for EOSC. The WG focused on four priority areas that form the major sections of this report: 1. Developing the next generation of FAIR and open science professionals; Presents a framework of all the EOSC actors (roles) in the EOSC ecosystem for whom skills and training is relevant. 2. Collaborating to enhance digital skills for FAIR and open science in Europe: Reviews organisational approaches to implement training activities and programmes, through the concept of competence centres. 3. Building a trusted and long-lasting and trusted knowledge hub of learning and training resources and related tools: Provides insights for an EOSC federated training catalogue as part of a sustainable training infrastructure that supports EOSC actors. 4. Influencing national open science policy for skills by supporting strategic leaders: Analyses the framing of digital skills required in EOSC in the wider European agenda for skills, to provide recommendations for Member States and Associated Countries on how to support EOSC in national skills policies and strategies. More info: [Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science](#)

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Figure 2. Home Page sections of the Diosi website

3.2 Website & Social media strategy & policy

Our audience will be mainly the Academia (Early Career Researchers and faculty in charge of their training), universities policy makers, university staff, but also governmental policy makers, private companies, media and general public. To reach these multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, as recommended by the EC (European Commission, 2014), all partners must be engaged with the communication of the project and their results, so we need some mechanisms to facilitate the publication on the different channels for all partners.

The general idea is to communicate, engage and generate awareness about Open Science (OS) and Open Innovation & Entrepreneurship (OI&E) for Early Career Researchers (ECR) sharing DIOSI, OS and OI&E stories, news and events. We are adopting a decentralized approach where every partner can propose contents for publishing on the website or in the official DIOSI social media accounts. Mechanisms for publishing will be through edition permission on the website for work packages representatives and automated process (filling a form for proposing contents to be published) for publishing in Twitter.

There are some key hashtags to be used in our social media accounts. An initial list of hashtags to be used and to follow is: #EarlyCareerResearchers, #openscience, #openresearch, #innovation, #entrepreneurship, #diosiproject, @AllianceYufe, #YUFE, #PhD, #opendata. Of course, this list will increase over time. For the Twitter account we recommend partners not to respond to (eventual) negative comments and make use of common sense and be aware that what we say is permanent. For YouTube videos, the preferred format is short (no more than 10 minutes), informal, entertaining and smart, a challenge. DIOSI events can help with interviews, contests and others formats to generate content.

3.3 Some Key Performance Indicators

All communication project must identify what's the aim to achieve. It's a good policy to define some Key Performance Indicators (KPI) of the channels used and make a follow up of the evolution of such KPIs. For the DIOSI project (a two year's project and only 18 months for communication activities) the KPIs defined are showed in the figure below. The evolution will be measured every 3 months.

		Outreach KPIs			
		Thresholds		Score	Assessment
		Lower	Upper	M10	M10
1	Project website views	4500	13500	0	Poor
2	Twitter followers	55	165	0	Poor
3	Views of YouTube videos	100	300	0	Poor
4	Number of pieces of mass media (press releases)	11	33	0	Poor
5	Trainers enrolled in OS train the trainers sessions	40	80	0	Poor
6	Number of Open Access publications in scientific journals	4	8	0	Poor
7	Posters and communications in conferences	6	18	0	Poor

Figure 3. KPIs of the DIOSI project

4. Bibliography

European Commission. (2014). *Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants* (Horizon 2020, p. 14). European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

